

1 **Influence of model resolution on the representation and**
2 **contribution of Antarctic Intermediate Water to**
3 **meridional salt transport in the Atlantic**

4 **Ophélie Meuriot** ^{1,4}, **Camille Lique** ², **Yves Plancherel** ¹, **Anne Marie Treguier**
5 ²

6 ¹Earth Science and Engineering, Imperial College London, London, UK
7 ²Univ. Brest, CNRS, IRD, Ifremer, Laboratoire d'Océanographie Physique et Spatiale (LOPS), IUEM,
8 Brest, 29280, France
9 ⁴Department of Technology, Management and Economics, Technical University of Denmark, 2800, Kgs.
10 Lyngby, Denmark

11 **Key Points:**

- 12 • Increasing model resolution improves the representation and northward spread of
13 Antarctic Intermediate Water.
14 • Improved representation is associated with high eddy kinetic energy and high mean
15 speed at intermediate depths in 1/4° and 1/12° models.
16 • Intermediate layer contributes to close to 30% of the northward meridional salt
17 transport in the Atlantic.

Corresponding author: Ophélie Meuriot, ophme@dtu.dk

Abstract

This study investigates the influence of model resolution on the representation of Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW) hydrographic properties and the role of eddies in the meridional transport of salt using three simulations from the HadGEM3-GC3.1 High-ResMIP family with varying ocean resolutions: the 1° LL model (parameterised eddies), the 1/4° MM model (eddy-present), and the 1/12° HH model (eddy-rich). The control-1950 simulation is compared with the WOA18 climatology. Results show that increasing model resolution improves the representation of AAIW core properties (temperature, salinity, and density) and its northward extent. The LL model shows a restricted low-salinity tongue compared to observations, whereas the MM and HH models are more aligned with observations. Regions of high eddy kinetic energy coincide with major AAIW pathways in the MM and HH models, while the LL model is not able to capture the fine scale of the western boundary currents. The meridional salt transport is decomposed into its mean and eddy component and a compensation of both terms is found in MM and HH. The intermediate layer contributes to close to 30% of the total northward salt transport. Although total and eddy meridional salt transports are similar between MM and HH for the intermediate layer, the HH model contains more coherent eddies with greater westward propagation, suggesting distinct underlying mechanisms of salt transport. The findings highlight the limitations of the LL model in reproducing AAIW properties and circulation, with major improvements in the MM and HH models.

Plain Language Summary

Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW) plays a key role in distributing heat and salt through the Atlantic Ocean, influencing large-scale circulation and climate. This study assesses how model ocean resolution affects the representation of AAIW using three simulations of the HadGEM3-GC3.1 model: a low-resolution model without resolved eddies, a medium-resolution eddy-present model, and a high-resolution eddy-rich model. Higher-resolution models provide a more accurate representation of AAIW properties (temperature, salinity, and density) and show its fresher waters extending further north than in the low resolution model. Analysis of meridional salt transport revealed that the intermediate layer accounts for close to 30% of the total northward salt transport. Results highlight the importance of higher resolution models for capturing intermediate-depth circulation.

1 Introduction

Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW) forms in the Southern Ocean and spreads northward in the Atlantic, Pacific and Indian basins, where it is easily identifiable as a mid-depth salinity minimum. AAIW extends in the North Atlantic along both the western boundary current up to the Caribbean Sea (van der Boog et al., 2022) and the eastern boundary current up to the south of Spain (Roque et al., 2019). The northward extent and pathways of AAIW in the North Atlantic are important as AAIW contributes to the northward limb of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) (Poggemann et al., 2018) and plays a role in the hydrological cycle by returning freshwater from high to low latitudes (Yao et al., 2017).

Although the low salinity signature of AAIW can be clearly identified in observations, coupled climate models struggle to represent key properties of AAIW in the Atlantic. In a study based on 11 Coupled Model Intercomparison Project 5 (CMIP5) models, Zhu et al. (2018) found that AAIW presents a salty bias and a reduced northward extent in the Atlantic compared to observations. Meuriot et al. (2022) showed that in UKESM1-0-LL, the Met Office Hadley Centre (MOHC) contribution to CMIP6, the core of AAIW is on average 0.3 psu saltier in the Atlantic compared to the Monthly Isopycnal Mixed-Layer Ocean Climatology (MIMOC) climatology, with the northward extent

68 of the AAIW core not reaching the equator in the model. In UKESM1-0-LL, the salty
 69 bias was found to increase rapidly from 20°S to the equator. The results in UKESM1-
 70 0-LL are symptomatic of the challenges faced by other models from the CMIP6 family
 71 to accurately represent AAIW in the Atlantic. Indeed, CMIP6 models were found to present
 72 an anomalous spread in AAIW core salinity in the Atlantic, north of the supergyre (Meuriot
 73 et al., 2024).

74 The majority of CMIP6 models contributing to the Diagnostic, Evaluation and Char-
 75 acterization of Klima (DECK) experiments have ocean resolutions of 1°, in which eddies
 76 are parameterised. Increasing ocean model resolution improves the representation of bound-
 77 ary currents, thermohaline fronts as well as the resolution of mesoscale eddies (Marzocchi
 78 et al., 2015; Hewitt et al., 2020; Tsujino et al., 2024). For instance, Marzocchi et al. (2015)
 79 found that the 1/12° NEMO ocean model represented more accurately the current system
 80 in the North Atlantic, such as the Gulf Stream separation and the subpolar gyre,
 81 compared to the coarse resolution (1° and 1/4°) equivalent versions. Hewitt et al. (2020)
 82 further highlight that higher resolution models are needed to represent intensified west-
 83 ern boundary currents such as the Agulhas Current, the Gulf Stream or the Kuroshio
 84 which have a typical width of 100 km.

85 HighResMIP models (Haarsma. et al., 2016) are run with ocean resolutions from
 86 0.1° to 1° to systematically assess the impact of horizontal resolution on the represen-
 87 tation of ocean physics. The impact of model resolution on the representation of the AMOC
 88 has been investigated by Roberts et al. (2020). The authors found that the increase in
 89 model resolution leads to a stronger AMOC at 26.5°N, in better agreement with obser-
 90 vations. In addition, Weijer and van Sebille (2014) investigated the role of eddies when
 91 looking at the inter-basin exchange between the Indian and Atlantic basins and found
 92 that transport is overestimated in non-eddy models due to the models' inability to
 93 represent the shedding of the Agulhas Rings into the Atlantic Ocean. In their analysis,
 94 Weijer and van Sebille (2014) show that the sharp salinity front found in observations
 95 between the saltier Indian basin and the fresher Atlantic basin cannot be identified in
 96 the Community Climate System Model, version 4 (CCSM4), which has a nominal ocean
 97 resolution of 1°.

98 It remains to be investigated how increased model resolution influences the rep-
 99 resentation of AAIW, and whether increasing model resolution can improve the limita-
 100 tions identified in typical CMIP models, such as high salinity bias at the depth of AAIW
 101 and the limited northward extent of AAIW (Zhu et al., 2018; Meuriot et al., 2022). The
 102 representation of salinity is particularly important to the meridional salt transport (quan-
 103 tified as the product of the velocity and salinity). It is particularly important in the At-
 104 lantic as the meridional salt transport is thought to control the stability of the merid-
 105 ional overturning circulation (Deshayes et al., 2013; Weijer et al., 2019). For instance,
 106 Treguier et al. (2012) quantified the contribution of eddies to the depth-integrated merid-
 107 ional salt transport in the North Atlantic in ocean models forced by an atmospheric re-
 108 analysis and found that the the eddy contribution at 40°N was almost twice as large in
 109 the 1/12° model as in the 1/4° model. No published studies so far have investigated the
 110 specific contribution of AAIW to the meridional salt transport in eddy coupled cli-
 111 mate models.

112 The HighResMIP experiment presents an opportunity to investigate how model res-
 113 olution influences the representation of AAIW. The aim of the study is to (i) assess the
 114 role of model resolution on the representation of AAIW hydrographic properties, extent
 115 and circulation in the Atlantic and (ii) to quantify the contribution of AAIW to the merid-
 116 ional salt transport. To that aim, we analyse the HadGEM3-GC3.1 (Hadley Centre Global
 117 Environment 3 - Global Coupled v3.1) models (Roberts et al., 2019) from the High-
 118 ResMIP experiment with nominal ocean resolutions ranging from 1° (eddy parameterised),
 119 1/4° (eddy-permitting) and 1/12° (eddy-rich). The study is structured as follows. Sec-
 120 tion 2 describes the models and definitions used in the analysis. Section 3 compares the

121 AAIW hydrographic properties in the models with observations. Section 4 investigates
 122 the differences in circulation patterns across the models. Section 5 quantifies the con-
 123 tribution of AAIW to the meridional salt transport. Finally, Section 6 provides a sum-
 124 mary of the results as well as perspectives for future works.

125 2 Methodology

126 2.1 Datasets

127 The HadGEM3-GC3.1 models used in this study were designed following the CMIP
 128 HighResMIP protocol (Haarsma. et al., 2016). One of the aims of HighResMIP is to as-
 129 sess the role of increased horizontal resolution on model mean state biases (Haarsma. et
 130 al., 2016). HighResMIP models use the same initial conditions and forcing as CMIP6
 131 models (Eyring et al., 2016) but HighResMIP simulations are shorter than CMIP6 DECK
 132 experiments due to the high cost associated with running the higher resolution models.
 133 A simplified aerosol parameterisation scheme (MACv2-SP) is used to enable compari-
 134 son across HighResMIP models (Stevens et al., 2017).

135 The HadGEM3-GC3.1 HighResMIP models are based on the same configuration
 136 as the HadGEM3-GC3.1 CMIP6 DECK model (Williams et al., 2018) apart from the
 137 aerosol parameterisation. The ocean component is GO6 (Storkey et al., 2018), which uses
 138 the Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean (NEMO) ocean model (Madec, 2017)
 139 on a tripolar grid with 75 vertical levels. The atmospheric model has 85 levels, extend-
 140 ing to an altitude of 85 km, and is set on a regular latitude-longitude grid. The sea ice
 141 model is CICE5.1 (Hunke & Lipscomb, 2010). More details on the model configuration
 142 can be found in Williams et al. (2018).

143 The HadGEM3-GC3.1 models from the HighResMIP protocol were run with var-
 144 ious combinations of oceanic and atmospheric horizontal resolutions (Roberts et al., 2019).
 145 The focus of this study is to investigate the influence of oceanic resolution on the mod-
 146 els’ ability to represent AAIW. The three models selected are the HadGEM3-GC3.1-LL,
 147 HadGEM3-GC3.1-MM and HadGEM3-GC3.1-HH, which are referred to hereafter as the
 148 LL, MM and HH models, respectively. Resolutions and spin up times are shown in Ta-
 149 ble 1. The LL model has an ocean resolution of 1° , with eddies parameterised using the
 150 Gent and McWilliams scheme (Gent & McWilliams, 1990). The MM and HH models have
 151 ocean resolutions of $1/4^\circ$ and $1/12^\circ$ and can be referred to as eddy-present and eddy-rich
 152 oceans, respectively.

Model	Ocean resolution (km)	Atmosphere resolution (km)
LL	100	250
MM	25	100
HH	8	50

Table 1. Nominal ocean and atmosphere resolutions (km), and initial condition for the LL, MM and HH models. Adapted from Roberts et al. (2019).

153 The 100-year-long control-1950 simulations are analysed here. They have a con-
 154 stant 1950s forcing and the last 10 years available of the simulation are used (2040-2049).
 155 For the control runs, the models are initialised by the end-state of a 30 years spin up run.
 156 The data were accessed from the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA) archive
 157 from the United Kingdom’s Joint Analysis System Meeting Infrastructure Needs super-
 158 data-cluster (JASMIN) platform. A 10-year average period is also used in Haarsma et

159 al. (2020) where future changes in surface salinity in three HighResMIP EC-Earth mod-
 160 els are investigated. More information regarding the HighResMIP forcing and simula-
 161 tions can be found in Roberts et al. (2019).

162 The temperature and salinity fields of the World Ocean Atlas 18 (WOA18) (Boyer
 163 et al., 2018) are used to compare with the hydrographic properties of the HadGEM3-
 164 GC3.1 models. The WOA18 climatological product is derived from a historical record
 165 of observations from 1955 to 2010 with temperature (Locarnini et al., 2018) and salin-
 166 ity (Zweng et al., 2019) provided at a $1/4^\circ$ resolution.

167 2.2 AAIW core and layer definitions

168 The AAIW core is defined as the depth of the vertical salinity minimum detected
 169 between 200 m and 2000 m. Properties such as temperature, salinity and water mass age
 170 are calculated at the depth level corresponding to the vertical salinity minimum for the
 171 LL, MM and HH models. Similarly to Meuriot et al. (2022), the Turner angle Tu is used
 172 to identify the vertical salinity extrema, with a value of $Tu = 45$ corresponding to both
 173 the salinity minimum and maximum. The Turner Angle is defined as $Tu = \arctan(\alpha T_z -$
 174 $\beta S_z, \alpha T_z + \beta S_z)$ where T_z and S_z are the vertical temperature and salinity gradients and
 175 α and β are the thermal and haline expansion coefficients respectively.

176 The isopycnals (potential density) which best fit the low salinity values in the HadGEM3-
 177 GC3.1 models (26.8 kg/m^3 and 27.4 kg/m^3) are used to define the layer corresponding
 178 to AAIW. Sørensen et al. (2001) used similar values (26.8 kg/m^3 and 27.5 kg/m^3) in a
 179 study using the MOM2 ocean model which they found to be in agreement with the Levitus
 180 (1982) observational dataset. The layer corresponding to AAIW is referred to as the in-
 181 termediate layer. The layers above and below the low salinity layer are hereafter referred
 182 to as the surface and deep layers. The distinction between the three layers is mainly used
 183 to differentiate the behaviour of the low salinity layer compared to the surrounding saltier
 184 layers as the focus of the study is to distinguish the contribution of AAIW to the salt
 185 transport. The contribution of the deep layer is included in the analysis but needs to be
 186 interpreted with caution as it includes distinct water masses such as North Atlantic Deep
 187 Water (NADW) and Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW).

188 2.3 Mean and eddy decompositions

189 The velocity can be decomposed using a Reynolds decomposition into $u = \bar{u} +$
 190 u' for the x component and into $v = \bar{v} + v'$ for the y component, where the overbar
 191 refers to the time mean and the prime to the time anomaly component. The mean speed
 192 is calculated here as $V = \sqrt{\bar{u}^2 + \bar{v}^2}$, and is used to reveal the main circulation path-
 193 ways. The Eddy Kinetic Energy (EKE), defined as $EKE = \frac{1}{2} (\overline{u'^2 + v'^2})$, is calculated
 194 to investigate the role of eddies in the circulation pathways.

195 Similarly to the velocity, the salinity can be decomposed into its mean and eddy
 196 components $S = \bar{S} + S'$. The northward transport of salt can be calculated as the prod-
 197 uct of the velocity in the y direction v and the salinity S . When time-averaged, a con-
 198 tribution from the averaged correlations between velocity and salinity anomalies arises
 199 from the product, which is referred to as "eddy transport" (Treguier et al., 2012). The
 200 total meridional time averaged salt transport can be decomposed as:

$$\int \int \overline{vS} dx dz = \int \int \bar{v} \bar{S} dx dz + \int \int \overline{v'S'} dx dz \quad (1)$$

201 where $\int \int \overline{vS} dx dz$ is the total salt transport, $\int \int \bar{v} \bar{S} dx dz$ is the mean salt trans-
 202 port and $\int \int \overline{v'S'} dx dz$ is the eddy salt transport. The total salt transport is expected
 203 to be non-divergent. The product vS is calculated online at the time step of the model
 204 and then averaged monthly. The salt transports are calculated based on a 10-year av-

205 erage period (between 2040 and 2049) using monthly fields. Transports are provided in
 206 the kg/s units. The computations are performed on the original ocean tripolar model
 207 grid.

208 **3 Improved representation of AAIW hydrographic properties with in-**
 209 **creased resolution**

210 Salinity cross sections at 33°W (Figure 1) as well as T/S (Temperature/Salinity)
 211 values at the depth of the AAIW (Figure 2) are compared between the LL, MM and HH
 212 models and in the WOA18 climatology, in order to assess whether the increase in res-
 213 olution leads to an improved representation of AAIW hydrographic properties.

Figure 1. Salinity section in the Atlantic at 33°W in the (a) LL, (b) MM, (c) HH models and (d) in WOA18. The black lines indicate the 26.8kg/m³ and 27.4kg/m³ isopycnals, the white lines correspond to a Tu angle of 45°. The 34.8 (36 psu) isohaline is marked by a blue (red) dashed line.

214 **3.1 Northward extent of AAIW**

215 In the LL, MM and HH models, the selected density contours to define the inter-
 216 mediate layer (26.8 kg/m³ and 27.4 kg/m³ in black in Figure 1) are found to follow closely
 217 the low salinity layer. The northward extent of the 34.8 isohaline (blue dashed in Fig-

ure 1) varies between the models and WOA18. The 34.8 isohaline contour reaches 15°S in the LL model compared to 7°N and 8°N in the MM and HH models, which are closer to a value of 10°N found in the WOA18. Salty biases in the intermediate layer in the subtropical regions therefore decrease with increasing resolution.

North of the extent of the low salinity values corresponding to AAIW, high salinity values can be identified in Figure 1. The high salinity values north of 15°S have a deeper extent in the LL model compared to MM, HH and WOA18. The 36 psu isohaline (marked by a red dashed line in Figure 1) extends down to 800 m in the LL model, whereas in the MM and HH models as well as in WOA18, the 36 psu isohaline is confined to the surface layer. A salinity bias can also be identified at depth with the bias decreasing with increased model resolution: at 750 m and 20°N, the salinity is around 35.6 psu in LL compared to 35.4 psu and 35.3 psu in MM and HH and 35.1 psu in WOA18. The salty biases identified in the North Atlantic are in agreement with Roberts et al. (2019) who find that the majority of HighResMIP models present such a bias at intermediate depths compared to observations at 26.5°N, although they highlight that the HadGEM3-GC3.1-HH model is one of the best models in minimising the salinity bias. It remains to be explored whether there is a relationship between the high salinity bias found in the MW and the high salinity bias found in AAIW.

3.2 Meridional changes in AAIW core density

The depth of the salinity minimum (upper white dashed line in Figure 1), differs between the LL, MM and HH models and in WOA18. In WOA18, the salinity minimum is found between the 26.8 kg/m³ and 27.4 kg/m³ isopycnals until 12°N, where it becomes denser and deeper. In the LL model, the salinity minimum is found between the 26.8 kg/m³ and 27.4 kg/m³ isopycnals until 20°S before deepening and densifying.

The northward densification of the AAIW core can also be identified on the T/S diagrams of the AAIW core (panels d, h, l and p in Figure 2). The colour of each square on the T/S diagrams shows the percentage of AAIW core T/S points found in a 0.05 psu x 0.3 °C bin. In WOA18, the density of the AAIW core ranges between 27 kg/m³ and 27.2 kg/m³ as it spreads northward. Its temperature increases from 3 °C to 7 °C and salinity increases from 34.1 psu to 34.8 psu. Changes in temperature and salinity largely compensate one another as AAIW spreads northward, resulting in a relatively constant density of the AAIW layer. In MM and HH, between 50°S and 7°N, the salinity at the core of AAIW increases from 34.3 psu to 34.8 psu in MM and from 34.2 psu to 34.8 psu in HH, but the temperature in these models remains relatively constant (between 4 °C and 5 °C). The results indicate that, although the northward salinification of the AAIW core in MM and HH appears to be in agreement with WOA18, there is an excessive densification of the AAIW core in MM and HH which is associated with a reduced northward warming of the AAIW core compared to WOA18.

3.3 South Atlantic T/S variations in AAIW

In LL, the AAIW core has a warm bias between 40°S and 20°S, with values between 5 °C and 7 °C compared to 3 °C and 5 °C in WOA18 (panels b, f, j and h in Figure 2). At low latitudes (between 20°S and the equator), a pronounced temperature gradient can be identified in LL between the Western boundary region and the East, which can also be identified in the T/S plot as two separate clusters of points with different densities (one group clustered between 26.8 kg/m³ and 27.2 kg/m³ and the other clustered between 27.3 kg/m³ and 27.6 kg/m³). The LL model is unable to simulate AAIW properties (temperature, salinity and density) adequately in the South Atlantic. The clear difference in density between the East Atlantic and the rest of the basin suggests that the salinity minimum in the East Atlantic corresponds to a different water mass to AAIW in LL. Looking at water age (i.e. time since last surface contact; panels c, g and k in Fig-

268 ure 2) confirms that the salinity minimum in the East Atlantic corresponds to a differ-
 269 ent regime, with high values in the LL model (> 90 years), contrasting with lower age
 270 values found in the MM and HH models (between 70 and 80 years) along the western
 271 boundary current all the way to the Northern Hemisphere, as well as along the equator
 272 in HH.

Figure 2. The salinity (a, e, i, m), temperature (b, f, j, n) and sea water age since surface contact (c, g, k) at the depth of the salinity minimum are shown on panels for the LL, MM, HH models and WOA18. T/S diagram (d, h, l, p) of the properties at the depth of the salinity minimum. The color indicates the % of grid points within a T/S 0.3°C by 0.05 psu bin.

273 In summary, the MM and HH models represent the northward extent of AAIW bet-
 274 ter than the LL model, with a limited densification of the AAIW core, similar to what
 275 is found in observations. The anomalous East-West differences in AAIW core prop-
 276 erties seen in the the LL model are not present in the MM and HH models and are also
 277 inconsistent with observations. The results are in agreement with Meuriot et al. (2024),
 278 where CMIP6 models were found to be unable to maintain AAIW’s core properties as
 279 it spreads northward towards the equator.

4 Impact of resolution on circulation patterns at intermediate depths in the Atlantic

The aim in this section is to assess how the increase in resolution influences the representation of AAIW's circulation in the Atlantic. Differences in large-scale circulation patterns between the parameterised eddy (LL), eddy present (MM) and eddy rich model (HH) lead to the differences in hydrographic properties consistent with those discussed in Section 3. The focus is here on the circulation of AAIW after formation. Stramma and England (1999) summarises the main currents found at the depth of AAIW (between 500 - 1200m) with from South to North: (1) the South Atlantic Subtropical Gyre between 45°S and 20°S, (2) the North Brazil Undercurrent between 20°S to 10°N and (3) the equatorial circulation. The mean speed and the EKE are calculated for the intermediate layer and averaged with depth (limited by the 26.8 kg/m³ and 27.4 kg/m³ isopycnals) and shown in Figure 3, panels a-c and d-f respectively.

4.1 South Atlantic Subtropical Gyre

The South Atlantic Subtropical Gyre at intermediate depths is composed of the South Atlantic Current, the Benguela Current and the Brazil Current. The South Atlantic Current can be identified in the models as the eastward mean flow between 45°S and 35°S and the Benguela Current as the westward flow between 35°S and 20°S. The averaged speed within the intermediate layer increases with resolution, with the HH model presenting the largest values compared to the MM and LL models. EKE increases with model resolution, with the LL model presenting values of EKE below 1 m²/s². The EKE values are large ($> 10^2$ m²/s²) in both the MM and HH models along the South Atlantic Current. The areas characterised by high averaged speeds in MM and HH correspond to regions with high EKE. In contrast with the LL model, high EKE values are found off the coast of South Africa in the MM and HH models, where Agulhas Rings are present.

4.2 North Brazil Undercurrent

The North Brazil Current can be identified between 20°S and the Caribbean Sea, with high mean speed values. In a description of the pathways of the AMOC, McCarthy et al. (2020) highlight the importance of the northward flow along the western boundary in the South Atlantic as a precursor to the Gulf Stream. In the LL, MM and HH models, the northward flow along the western boundary of South America can be identified between 20°S and 8°N. The averaged speed in the western boundary current region are lower in the LL model (between 0.05 m/s and 0.08 m/s) compared to the MM and HH models (averaged speed greater than 0.12 m/s). Although EKE values are higher than elsewhere along the western boundary current in the LL model, the EKE values in LL are 10 times smaller than in the MM and HH models. In the LL model, no salinity minimum can be found in the Caribbean Sea (Figure 2), suggesting that higher resolution is needed to resolve the injection of AAIW into the Caribbean Sea.

4.3 Equatorial circulation

The main circulation pathways at the equator include the westward flowing Equatorial Intermediate Current (EIC), as well as the Northern Intermediate Countercurrent (NICC) and the Southern Intermediate Countercurrent (SICC) going eastward north and south of the EIC (Stramma & England, 1999). In the LL model, mean speed values are very weak between 15°S and 10°N, highlighting the model limitations in representing the complex structure of the equatorial pathways at intermediate depths. In the MM and HH models, multiple branches of current can be identified in the equatorial region between 5°S and 5°N. The presence of higher mean speed values suggests that the MM and HH models present some pathways across the equator at intermediate depths which is

328 not the case in LL model. Large differences in EKE values can be found at the equator
 329 with values close to $100 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$ in MM compared to $10 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$ in LL.

Figure 3. (a) Mean speed averaged in the intermediate layer (b) EKE averaged in the intermediate layer for the LL, MM and HH models respectively.)

330 In the LL, MM and HH models, the South Equatorial Current (SEC) can be identified,
 331 as well as the Equatorial Undercurrent (EUC) down to 400 m as a positive east-
 332 ward velocity (Figure 4). Both the MM and HH models have eastward velocities at depths
 333 between 400 m and 600 m; however, in LL, the velocities are very weak in the inter-
 334 mediate layer (marked by the grey density dashed line in Figure 3). Alternating layers of
 335 eastward and westward velocities can be found in the MM and HH models with thick-
 336 nesses of 100-200 m, starting with an eastward flowing layer located at the depth of the
 337 salinity minimum (45° contour in black in Figure 4). The alternating layers in MM and
 338 HH are in agreement with the schematic of the vertical structure of the equatorial cur-
 339 rent system presented by Ménesguen et al. (2019). At the equator, the westward flow-
 340 ing SEC is found at the surface, with the eastward flowing EUC between 100 m and 300
 341 m and the EIC between 300 m and 600 m (Ménésguen et al., 2019). Beneath 600 m,
 342 the intermediate and deep equatorial circulations consist of a complex system of zonal jets.
 343 The Equatorial Deep Jets (EDJ) are found between 600 m and 1600 m and consist of
 344 alternating vertical zonal currents of a few hundreds of meters (Ménésguen et al., 2019).
 345 It is speculated here that the alternating layers in MM and HH could be due to the mod-
 346 els' ability to represent the equatorial dynamics better than in LL and hence the com-
 347 plex pattern of the EDJ is able to be identified. This is in agreement with Duteil et al.
 348 (2021) where the authors show that in the Pacific the Equatorial Intermediate Current
 349 System (which includes the series of jets from below the thermocline to 2000 m) is only
 350 present in models of resolution of $1/4^\circ$ or higher.

351 In LL, in the salinity cross sections at the equator (Figure 4, panels d, e and f), the
 352 salinity minimum (marked by the 45° contour line) falls below the defined intermediate
 353 layer. The lowest value of the salinity minimum in LL is found on the eastern bound-
 354 ary beneath the intermediate layer and is equal to 34.8 psu whereas in the MM and HH
 355 models the lowest value of the salinity minimum is equal to 34.7 psu and 34.6 psu and

356 is located on the western boundary within the intermediate layer. The results suggest
 357 that the northward western boundary current needs to be correctly represented for AAIW
 358 to be advected eastward at the equator and that the coarse resolution of 1° in the LL
 359 model is not suitable to resolve the complex dynamics at play at the equator.

Figure 4. Salinity sections at the equator (a-c), eastward velocity (x component) at the equator in the LL, MM and HH models. The white dashed lines correspond to the 26.8kg/m^3 and 27.4kg/m^3 density isopycnals and the black lines correspond to the 45° Turner angle value.

360 5 AAIW contribution to the meridional salt transport and role of eddies

361

362 The MM and HH models adequately simulate both the hydrographic properties and
 363 circulation patterns of AAIW (Sections 3 and 4). The aim here is to quantify, in these
 364 two models, the contribution of eddies to the meridional salt transport in the Atlantic
 365 as well as to quantify the contribution of AAIW to the total the meridional salt
 366 transport. The LL model eddy contribution is not included in this section as eddies in that
 367 model are parameterised.

368 5.1 Decomposition between total, mean and eddy salt transports

369 Figure 5 shows the total, mean and eddy salt transports for the MM and HH mod-
 370 els. Similarly to Treguier et al. (2012), the total salt transport at 30°S is subtracted from
 371 the total and mean transports ($-34.1 \cdot 10^6 \text{ kg/s}$ and $-38.2 \cdot 10^6 \text{ kg/s}$ in MM and HH re-
 372 spectively). Both the MM and HH models present similar latitudinal eddy salt trans-
 373 port structures with local peak values found at the tip of South Africa (34°S), at 1°S and
 374 at 12°N . The divergence in salt transports between 34°S and 1°S as well as between 1°S
 375 and 12°N are presented in Table 5.1. A divergence in eddy salt transport between 34°S
 376 and 1°S of $7.4 \cdot 10^6 \text{ kg/s}$ and $7.5 \cdot 10^6 \text{ kg/s}$ can be identified in the MM and HH mod-
 377 els respectively. The eddy salt transport convergence between 1°S and 12°N is larger in
 378 HH than in MM (9.8 vs $6.6 \cdot 10^6 \text{ kg/s}$ respectively). North of the equator, the eddy salt
 379 transport is smaller in MM compared to HH, with a peak value of $-6.5 \cdot 10^6 \text{ kg/s}$ at 12°N
 380 in MM compared to $-3.9 \cdot 10^6 \text{ kg/s}$ in HH. As expected, eddies contribute to the flux of
 381 salt out of the subtropical gyre (a region of net evaporation) and bring salt into the tropi-
 382 cal region where freshwater input from precipitations and runoff dominates. The merid-
 383 ional salt transports are dependent on the resolution of the model, which is in agreement
 384 with the study of Treguier et al. (2012), in which the meridional salt transports were cal-

385 culated in two regional models of the North Atlantic ($1/12^\circ$ and $1/4^\circ$ resolution) and a
 386 global model ($1/4^\circ$ resolution) forced with a reanalysis.

	South Atlantic ($34^\circ\text{S} - 1^\circ\text{S}$)		Tropical Atlantic ($1^\circ\text{S} - 12^\circ\text{N}$)	
	MM	HH	MM	HH
F div [Sv]	-0.6	-0.6	0.3	0.3
$\overline{\text{FS}}$ div [$\times 10^6$ kg/s]	-20.5	-21.8	10.1	11.4
VSO Total div [$\times 10^6$ kg/s]	-0.8	-0.3	0.5	0.9
VSO Mean div [$\times 10^6$ kg/s]	-7.4	-7.5	6.6	9.8
VSO Eddy div [$\times 10^6$ kg/s]	6.6	7.1	-6.1	-8.9
dS/dT [$\times 10^6$ kg/s]	0.8	0.5	0.8	0.4

Table 2. Volume flux divergence (F div), divergence of the product of the volume flux and the zonal mean salinity ($\overline{\text{FS}}$ div), total, mean and eddy salt transport divergence (VSO total, mean and eddy div respectively) and salt content change over 10 years dS/dT in the South ($34^\circ\text{S} - 1^\circ\text{S}$) and Tropical ($1^\circ\text{S} - 12^\circ\text{N}$) Atlantic.

387 In both MM and HH, there is a compensation between the mean and eddy compo-
 388 nents. This is due to the fact that in an ocean basin, the divergence of the total salt
 389 transport (the sum of the advective and diffusive components) is equal to the change in
 390 salt content (see Treguier et al. (2012), their Equation 7). Regional salt content changes
 391 over the 10 years of our analysis are found to be small, because we use control simula-
 392 tions without any climate change signal, and there is only a weak salinity drift after a
 393 100-year integration (Table 2). A compensation between the eddy and mean salt trans-
 394 port was also found in Treguier et al. (2012) in $1/12^\circ$ and $1/4^\circ$ models forced by a re-
 395 analysis. Similarly to Treguier et al. (2012), an almost complete compensation between
 396 mean and eddy is achieved in the HH model and to a lesser degree in the MM model in
 397 the South Atlantic. The compensation is less complete in the tropical Atlantic (Table
 398 2). In both regions, the total advective salt flux divergence (mean+eddy) is of the same
 399 order of magnitude as the salt content change (Table 2), but is not equal to it. We can-
 400 not compute a closed salt budget for two reasons: firstly, there is a missing term, the pa-
 401 rameterised diffusive salt flux, which we could not compute independently from the model
 402 archives. Secondly, the estimation of the change in salt content is not exact because only
 403 monthly averages are available. In the South Atlantic, a larger diffusive flux in MM com-
 404 pared with HH would be consistent with the fact that eddies are only partially resolved
 405 in MM. In the tropical Atlantic, a more precise estimate of the change in salt content
 406 would probably improve the budget, because the seasonal cycle has a sizeable contribu-
 407 tion to the velocity-salinity correlation there (Treguier et al., 2012; Tréguier et al., 2014).

408 Because the E-P-R forcing (evaporation minus precipitation minus coastal runoff
 409 patterns) does not carry any salt, comparing the amplitude of the eddy salt flux with
 410 the forcing requires combining the volume conservation with the salt conservation equa-
 411 tion. The calculation of freshwater transports is one way to do this, but this method is
 412 not recommended in climate models (Schauer & Losch, 2019) because it involves an ar-
 413 bitrary reference salinity. Another method, advocated by Tréguier et al. (2014), is to fur-
 414 ther decompose the time mean velocity into the zonally and depth averaged velocity $\langle V \rangle$
 415 and a recirculation velocity which is the anomaly relative to the zonal-depth mean.
 416 The salt flux divergence due to the zonal-depth averaged velocity is directly forced by
 417 E-P-R due to the requirement for exact volume conservation in the model (Tréguier et
 418 al., 2014). Its value, denoted as $\overline{\text{FS}}$, is indicated in Table 2 for the South Atlantic and

419 the tropical region. As it is calculated from monthly fields, it is an approximation but
 420 it helps put in perspective the amplitude of the eddy salt flux . In the South Atlantic,
 421 net evaporation causes a volume loss of 0.6 Sv, which induces a compensating inflow of
 422 salt $\overline{F_S}$ of about $-21 \cdot 10^6$ kg/s. The divergence of the time-mean advective salt trans-
 423 port, $-7.5 \cdot 10^6$ kg/s, is much less: this demonstrates that the time-mean, zonally and
 424 depth-varying recirculations export salt ($13.5 \cdot 10^6$ kg/s). The eddy flux of salt thus rep-
 425 represents about one third of the salt export required to compensate the net evaporation,
 426 the time-mean recirculations account for the other two thirds.

Figure 5. Total, mean and eddy salt transport calculated for the full depth in blue, orange and green respectively. The total and mean value at 30°S is subtracted from the total and mean transports. The dashed lines correspond to the MM model and the full lines to the HH model.

427 Our results provide additional evidence supporting the findings of Treguier et al.
 428 (2012) in the North Atlantic, showing that (i) the eddy salt transport is significant and
 429 that (ii) there is a compensation between mean and eddy salt transport in the South At-
 430 lantic.

431 5.2 Contribution of AAIW to the meridional salt transport

432 The transports are further divided between the surface, intermediate and deep lay-
 433 ers (Figure 6). In all models, the total salt transport is northward for the surface and
 434 intermediate layers and is compensated by a southward salt transport in the deep layer.
 435 The total salt transport is larger in the HH model in both the surface and deep layers
 436 compared to the MM and LL models. However, for the intermediate layer, the total salt
 437 transport presents similar values in both the MM and HH models (around $180 \cdot 10^6$ kg/s).

438 The specificity of the intermediate layer, compared to the surface layer, is that it
 439 transports water masses with lower salinity. Although the MM and HH models present
 440 the same values of total salt transport, their zonal mean salinity differ, with lower val-
 441 ues in HH compared to MM (a difference of 0.2 psu at 10°S). Zhu et al. (2018) assesses
 442 the impact of salinity and temperature biases at intermediate depths in the Atlantic in
 443 experiments using the POP2 ocean model, where the salinity and temperature in spec-
 444 ific locations are restored to a monthly climatology from observations. Based on a zonal
 445 average at 34°S in the Atlantic, the POP2 ocean model is found to have a fresh bias at
 446 the surface (0.2 psu) and a salty bias at intermediate depths (0.2 psu at a depth of 800
 447 m). In an experiment with the salinity and temperature restored to their values at a depth
 448 of 1200 m between 30°S and 60°S in the Atlantic basin, Zhu et al. (2018) show that the

449 AMOC freshwater export from the intermediate depth is enhanced with an overturning
 450 freshwater flux at 34°S equal to -0.13 Sv (compared to -0.077 Sv in the control run), which
 451 falls in the range of values obtained from observations (between -0.34 and -0.1 Sv). Zhu
 452 et al. (2018) highlight that the AAIW bias contributes to the biased AMOC freshwater
 453 export. Although the sole influence of the salty bias on the meridional salt transport can-
 454 not be isolated due to differences in model resolution, the fresher and more realistic salinity
 455 at intermediate depths in HH may be linked to the stronger northward transport in
 456 HH compared to MM.

Figure 6. (a) Total salt transport [$\times 10^6$ kg/s], (b) contribution of the eddy salt transport to the total salt transport [%] (c) Zonal mean salinity at the surface, intermediate and deep layers (grey, red and purple respectively). The dashed lines correspond to the MM model and the full lines to the HH model.

457 The results show that the HH model presents a larger total salt transport at the
 458 surface compared to the MM model. However, the intermediate layer contribution to the
 459 total northward salt transport is non-negligible and corresponds to close to 30% of the
 460 total northward salt transport (here defined as the sum of surface and intermediate to-
 461 tal northward salt transport) in the MM and HH models at 20°S. The eddy contribu-
 462 tion of the salt transport is similar in both MM and HH. The eddy salt transport is most
 463 important between the equator and 20°N where the eddy salt transport contributes to
 464 over 0.5% of the total salt transport at 15°N for the surface and intermediate layers (Fig-
 465 ure 6). It is unclear whether the small eddy meridional transport values between 25°S
 466 and the equator in both MM and HH are due to a low eddy activity or whether it is an
 467 artifact of the zonal sum or vertical sum across the layer with opposite eddy contribu-
 468 tions canceling out. To investigate further the spatial variability of the total and eddy
 469 salt transport, zonal and vertical variations of the salt transport with depth are explored
 470 in the HH model.

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5.3 Spatial variability of the salt transport in the HH model

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The salinity, total salt transport and eddy salt transport are shown in three sections (30°S, 15°S and 15°N) in the HH model (Figure 7). The three sections are selected to look at two sections where the eddy salt transport is the largest (30°S and 15°N) and a section where the eddy salt transport is negligible (15°S) (Figure 5). Similarly to Figure 6, panel d, an increase in salinity with latitude of the intermediate layer can be identified between the three sections (panels a, b and c). At 30°S, the intermediate layer presents values between 34.4-34.6 psu whereas at 15°S and 15°N the values vary between 34.6-34.8 psu and 34.9-35.2 psu, respectively. However, the increase in salinity is not uniform zonally throughout the layer, with lower salinity values along the western side of the section at 15°S (~ 34.6 psu) and in the Caribbean Sea at 15°N (~ 34.6 psu).

Figure 7. Salinity sections (a-c), total salt transport sections (d-f) and eddy salt transport sections (g-i) at 30°S, 15°S and 15°N in the HH model. The isopycnals corresponding to AAIW (26.8 and 27.4 kg/m^3) are marked as black lines and the Tu angle of 45° corresponding to vertical salinity extrema as grey dashed lines.

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The total salt transport (panels d, e and f) is dominant at the western boundary in both the 15°S and 30°S sections, with negative values at all depths in the 30°S section (between the surface and 2000 m with a magnitude greater than $0.5 \cdot 10^6$ kg/s) and positive values for the surface and intermediate layers (between the surface and 1000 m with a magnitude greater than $0.5 \cdot 10^6$ kg/s), and negative values for the deep layer (below 1000 m, with a magnitude greater than $0.5 \cdot 10^6$ kg/s) in the 15°S section. At 15°N, the southward flow along the western boundary current can be identified in the deep layer at 60°W below 1000 m, with the surface and intermediate layers presenting a total salt transport directed northward.

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The three sections present different vertical eddy salt transport structures, with significant longitudinal variations (panels g, h and i). At 30°S, the highest values of eddy salt transport are found on the eastern side of the section between 0°E and 20°E , with positive values above 500 m and negative values below. In the 15°S section, the eddy salt transport is overall weaker, with alternating negative and positive values at the intermediate layer of 200 kg/s at the western boundary between 30°W and 40°W . At 15°N, the eddy salt transport is highest in the Caribbean Sea between 55°W and 85°W in the surface and intermediate layer (between the surface and 1000 m) with values close to 0

499 in the deep layer. Our results are in agreement with the $v'S'$ patterns shown in Treguier
 500 et al. (2012) at 15°N, where the largest values are also found in the Caribbean Sea. Sim-
 501 ilar patterns are found with a negative eddy salt transport between 0 m and 100 m and
 502 positive eddy salt transport between 100 m and 900 m at the western boundary. The
 503 pattern is reversed in the remainder of the Caribbean Sea with positive values above 100
 504 m and negative values below, which is again consistent with the results of Treguier et
 505 al. (2012). The results show that although the eddy contribution appears to be small when
 506 integrated over the intermediate layer, it is composed of a positive and negative contri-
 507 bution which compensate for each other. The alternating sign of the eddy contribution
 508 is associated with the alternating sign of the salinity anomaly. Indeed, the local deep-
 509 ening (shallowing) of the salinity minimum due to the presence of an anticyclonic (cy-
 510 clonic) eddy leads to a positive (negative) anomaly in salinity above the salinity min-
 511 imum and negative (positive) salinity anomaly below the salinity minimum.

512 To summarise, both MM and HH models show that there is a compensation be-
 513 tween the mean and eddy component. AAIW accounts for about 30% of the northward
 514 salt transport. Spatially, the total salt transport is strongest along western boundaries,
 515 while eddy contributions vary locally with alternating positive and negative patterns due
 516 to the presence of eddies.

517 5.4 Differences in coherent eddy structures in MM and HH models

518 In the analysis presented so far, we have defined an eddy term as a deviation from
 519 the time mean, meaning that it encompasses not only the coherent vortices but also the
 520 meanders and the seasonal and interannual variations of the currents and salinity fields.
 521 Based on this definition, we show that the eddy contribution in the intermediate layer
 522 is of similar magnitude in both the MM and HH models. One may hence question how
 523 the coherent eddy structures compare across both the MM and HH models. Figure 8 shows
 524 a snap shot of salinity anomalies at intermediate depths (January 2040), where coher-
 525 ent eddies are identified as closed contours of salinity anomalies of 0.1 psu for MM (panel
 526 a) and HH (panel b). The percentage of time steps where coherent eddies are present
 527 at a given grid point over the 10-year simulation are shown in panels c and d respectively
 528 for MM and HH. The number of coherent eddies is greater with tracks extending fur-
 529 ther west into the Atlantic in HH compared to MM. The pathways and westward extent
 530 of the coherent eddies in HH are in agreement with the pathways identified in Guerra
 531 et al. (2022) using satellite data. The results hence highlight that, although on a time
 532 average perspective, the eddy component appears to be of similar magnitude in both MM
 533 and HH, the physical processes behind the salt transport are different.

534 6 Conclusions

535 The aim of the study was to investigate the impact of model resolution on the rep-
 536 resentation of AAIW hydrographic properties (temperature, salinity and density) as well
 537 as to quantify the contribution of eddies to the meridional transport of salt. Three mod-
 538 els from the HadGEM3-GC3.1 HighResMIP family were assessed in the study: the 1°
 539 LL model (parameterised eddies), the 1/4° MM model (eddy-present) and the 1/12° HH
 540 (eddy-rich). The control-1950 simulation of each model was analyzed over a 10-year av-
 541 erage (2040-2049) and the results were compared to the WOA18 climatology.

542 An increase in model resolution was shown to improve the representation of AAIW
 543 core properties (temperature, salinity and density) as well as its northward extent. The
 544 LL model was found to present some deficiencies compared to WOA18 with a limited
 545 northward extent of the low salinity tongue with the 34.8 psu isohaline at 33°W reach-
 546 ing 15°S compared to 10°N in WOA18. The MM and HH models present some improve-
 547 ments with the 34.8 psu at 33°W reaching 7°N and 8°N respectively. Regions of high EKE
 548 are found at the locations of the key pathways of AAIW (the South Atlantic Subtrop-

Figure 8. Salinity anomaly at 565 m for one time step (January 2040) in the MM and HH models. Coherent eddies are here identified by a closed contour of a 0.1 psu anomaly are marked in black. The % of monthly time steps (over a 10 year period) with eddies present in the MM and HH models respectively.

549 ical Gyre, northward western boundary currents and equatorial currents) which corre-
 550 spond to locations of strong mean currents in the MM and HH models. The LL model
 551 is unable to represent the EIC and presents weaker currents along the northward west-
 552 ern boundary current and South Atlantic Subtropical Gyre.

553 The meridional salt transport is calculated in the MM and HH models with a de-
 554 composition of the total meridional salt transport into a mean and eddy component. Both
 555 models show a compensation between the mean and eddy components. The total and
 556 eddy meridional salt transports were further decomposed into the surface, intermediate
 557 and deep layers. The intermediate layer contributes close to 30% of the total northward
 558 transport in the MM and HH models. The MM and HH models present similar total and
 559 eddy salt transport values, although the salinity of the HH layer is lower than in the MM
 560 model. An analysis of the position and number of coherent eddy structures in the MM
 561 and HH models highlights that, although on a time average, the eddy salt transport val-
 562 ues estimated from a classical Reynolds decomposition are similar, the HH model presents
 563 a higher number of coherent eddies which propagate further west than in MM. The re-
 564 sults suggest that the models present different physical processes at play to determine
 565 the meridional salt transport.

566 The study highlights that model resolution greater than 1° is needed to study the
 567 hydrographic properties and circulation at intermediate depths. The reduced extent of
 568 AAIW in the LL model, with large biases in the eastern side of the Atlantic, seems to
 569 be associated with low eastward velocities at the equator at intermediate depth. Few stud-
 570 ies have investigated the role of the equatorial dynamics in the transport of AAIW. Oudot
 571 et al. (1999) looked at the flow of intermediate water across the equator using hydrographic
 572 data from research cruises but did not study the westward propagation of the water mass.
 573 Jochum and Malanotte-Rizzoli (2003) investigated the flow of AAIW along the equator
 574 in an ocean GCM and argues that the westward propagation of AAIW is due to small
 575 velocities rather than strong zonal currents from jets located at intermediate depths. More
 576 recently, the role of the EDJs in the equatorial circulation has been highlighted both in

577 modelling works (Taguchi et al., 2012) as well as in observations (Youngs & Johnson,
578 2015). Further work is needed to investigate the role of the EDJs on the circulation of
579 AAIW.

580 The main improvements in the representation of AAIW’s core properties (temper-
581 ature, salinity, density) were found going from the LL model to the MM model (1° to
582 $1/4^\circ$) with a more limited improvement in the core properties between MM and HH ($1/4^\circ$
583 to $1/12^\circ$). However, the results highlight the need to assess AAIW with caution in low
584 resolution models (1°) at low latitudes due to its reduced northward extent. More work
585 is needed to assess whether the improvements with increased resolution of AAIW in HadGEM3-
586 GC3.1 are model specific or whether similar results can be found in other HighResMIP
587 models.

588 Open Research Section

589 The HighResMIP data was accessed through the Centre for Environmental Data
590 Analysis (CEDA) archive and processed on JASMIN, the United Kingdom’s data anal-
591 ysis facility for environmental science. The HighResMIP data can be downloaded on [https://
592 esgf-index1.ceda.ac.uk/projects/esgf-ceda/](https://esgf-index1.ceda.ac.uk/projects/esgf-ceda/). The WOA18 data was accessed through
593 the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA): [https://www.ncei.noaa
594 .gov/access/world-ocean-atlas-2018/](https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/world-ocean-atlas-2018/).

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604 References

- 605 Boyer, T. P., García, H. E., Locarnini, R. A., Zweng, M. M., Mishonov, A. V., Rea-
606 gan, J. R., ... others (2018). World ocean atlas.
- 607 Deshayes, J., Tréguier, A.-M., Barnier, B., Lecomte, A., Sommer, J. L., Molines,
608 J.-M., ... others (2013). Oceanic hindcast simulations at high resolution sug-
609 gest that the atlantic moc is bistable. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *40*(12),
610 3069–3073.
- 611 Duteil, O., Frenger, I., & Getzlaff, J. (2021). The riddle of eastern tropical Pacific
612 Ocean oxygen levels: The role of the supply by intermediate-depth waters.
613 *Ocean Science*, *17*(5), 1489–1507. doi: 10.5194/OS-17-1489-2021
- 614 Eyring, V., Bony, S., Meehl, G. A., Senior, C. A., Stevens, B., Stouffer, R. J., &
615 Taylor, K. E. (2016). Overview of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
616 Phase 6 (CMIP6) experimental design and organization. *Geosci. Model Dev*,
617 *9*. doi: 10.5194/gmd-9-1937-2016
- 618 Gent, P. R., & McWilliams, J. C. (1990). Isopycnal Mixing in Ocean Circulation
619 Models. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, *20*(1), 150–155. doi: [https://doi
620 .org/10.1175/1520-0485\(1990\)020<0150:IMIOCM>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(1990)020<0150:IMIOCM>2.0.CO;2)
- 621 Guerra, L. A. A., Mill, G. N., & Paiva, A. M. (2022). Observing the spread of ag-
622 ulhas leakage into the western south atlantic by tracking mode waters within
623 ocean rings. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, *9*, 958733.
- 624 Haarsma., Roberts, M. J., Vidale, P. L., Catherine, A., Bellucci, A., Bao, Q., ...

- 625 Von Storch, J. S. (2016). High Resolution Model Intercomparison Project
626 (HighResMIP v1.0) for CMIP6. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 9(11),
627 4185–4208. doi: 10.5194/gmd-9-4185-2016
- 628 Haarsma, R., Acosta, M., Bakhshi, R., Bretonnière, P. A., Caron, L. P., Castrillo,
629 M., ... Wyser, K. (2020, 8). HighResMIP versions of EC-Earth: EC-Earth3P
630 and EC-Earth3P-HR - Description, model computational performance and
631 basic validation. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 13(8), 3507–3527. doi:
632 10.5194/GMD-13-3507-2020
- 633 Hewitt, H. T., Roberts, M., Mathiot, P., Biastoch, A., Blockley, E., Chas-
634 signet, E. P., ... Zhang, Q. (2020). *Resolving and Parameterising the*
635 *Ocean Mesoscale in Earth System Models* (Vol. 6) (No. 4). doi: 10.1007/
636 s40641-020-00164-w
- 637 Hunke, E. C., & Lipscomb, W. H. (2010). CICE : the Los Alamos Sea Ice Model
638 Documentation and Software User's Manual Version 4.1. *Technical Report LA-*
639 *CC-06-012*, 1–76.
- 640 Jochum, M., & Malanotte-Rizzoli, P. (2003). The flow of AAIW along the equator.
641 *Elsevier Oceanography Series*, 68(C), 193–212. doi: 10.1016/S0422-9894(03)
642 80147-2
- 643 Levitus, S. (1982). *Climatological atlas of the world ocean* (Vol. 13). US Department
644 of Commerce, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration.
- 645 Locarnini, M., Mishonov, A., Baranova, O., Boyer, T., Zweng, M., Garcia, H., ...
646 others (2018). World ocean atlas 2018, volume 1: Temperature.
- 647 Madec, G. (2017). NEMO ocean engine. *Note du Pôle de modélisation, Institut*
648 *Pierre-Simon Laplace (IPSL)*(27), 357pp. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.1472492
- 649 Marzocchi, A., Hirschi, J. J., Holliday, N. P., Cunningham, S. A., Blaker, A. T.,
650 & Coward, A. C. (2015). The North Atlantic subpolar circulation in an
651 eddy-resolving global ocean model. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 142. doi:
652 10.1016/j.jmarsys.2014.10.007
- 653 McCarthy, G. D., Brown, P. J., Flagg, C. N., Goni, G., Houpert, L., Hughes, C. W.,
654 ... Smeed, D. A. (2020). *Sustainable Observations of the AMOC: Methodology*
655 *and Technology* (Vol. 58) (No. 1). doi: 10.1029/2019RG000654
- 656 Ménesguen, C., Delpech, A., Marin, F., Cravatte, S., Schopp, R., & Morel, Y.
657 (2019). Observations and Mechanisms for the Formation of Deep Equator-
658 rial and Tropical Circulation. *Earth and Space Science*, 6(3), 370–386. doi:
659 10.1029/2018EA000438
- 660 Meuriot, O., Lique, C., & Plancherel, Y. (2022). Properties, sensitivity, and stability
661 of the Southern Hemisphere salinity minimum layer in the UKESM1 model.
662 *Climate Dynamics*, 1, 1–21. doi: 10.1007/S00382-022-06304-2/METRICS
- 663 Meuriot, O., Lique, C., & Plancherel, Y. (2024). Influence of the southern hemi-
664 sphere supergyre on antarctic intermediate water properties in cmip6 models.
665 *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 129(12), e2024JC021140.
- 666 Oudot, C., Ternon, J. F., Andrié, . C., Braga, E. S., & Morin5, P. (1999). On the
667 crossing of the equator by intermediate water masses in the Western Atlantic
668 Ocean : identification and pathways of Antartic intermediate water and upper
669 circumpolar water. *JOURNAL OF GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH*, 104(C9),
670 911–931.
- 671 Poggemann, D. W., Nürnberg, D., Hathorne, E. C., Frank, M., Rath, W., Reißig, S.,
672 & Bahr, A. (2018). Deglacial Heat Uptake by the Southern Ocean and Rapid
673 Northward Redistribution Via Antarctic Intermediate Water. *Paleoceanography*
674 *and Paleoclimatology*, 33(11), 1292–1305. doi: 10.1029/2017PA003284
- 675 Roberts, M. J., Baker, A., Blockley, E. W., Calvert, D., Coward, A., Hewitt, H. T.,
676 ... Luigi Vidale, P. (2019). Description of the resolution hierarchy of the
677 global coupled HadGEM3-GC3.1 model as used in CMIP6 HighResMIP
678 experiments. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12(12), 4999–5028. doi:
679 10.5194/GMD-12-4999-2019

- 680 Roberts, M. J., Jackson, L. C., Roberts, C. D., Meccia, V., Docquier, D., Koenigk,
681 T., . . . Wu, L. (2020, 8). Sensitivity of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning
682 Circulation to Model Resolution in CMIP6 HighResMIP Simulations and
683 Implications for Future Changes. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth
684 Systems*, *12*(8). doi: 10.1029/2019MS002014
- 685 Roque, D., Parras-Berrocal, I., Bruno, M., Sánchez-Leal, R., & Javier Hernández-
686 Molina, F. (2019). Seasonal variability of intermediate water masses in the
687 Gulf of Cádiz: Implications of the Antarctic and subarctic seesaw. *Ocean
688 Science*, *15*(5), 1381–1397. doi: 10.5194/os-15-1381-2019
- 689 Schauer, U., & Losch, M. (2019). “freshwater” in the ocean is not a useful parameter
690 in climate research. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, *49*(9), 2309–2321.
- 691 Sørensen, J. V. T., Ribbe, J., & Shaffer, G. (2001). Antarctic Intermediate Wa-
692 ter Mass Formation in Ocean General Circulation Models. *Journal of Physical
693 Oceanography*, *31*(11), 3295–3311. doi: 10.1175/1520-0485(2001)031
- 694 Stevens, B., Fiedler, S., Kinne, S., Peters, K., Rast, S., Müsse, J., . . . Mauritsen,
695 T. (2017). MACv2-SP: a parameterization of anthropogenic aerosol optical
696 properties and an associated Twomey effect for use in CMIP6. *Geosci. Model
697 Dev*, *10*, 433–452. doi: 10.5194/gmd-10-433-2017
- 698 Storkey, D., Blaker, A. T., Mathiot, P., Megann, A., Aksenov, Y., Blockley, E. W.,
699 . . . Sinha, B. (2018, 8). UK Global Ocean GO6 and GO7: A traceable hierar-
700 chy of model resolutions. *Geoscientific Model Development*, *11*(8), 3187–3213.
701 doi: 10.5194/GMD-11-3187-2018
- 702 Stramma, L., & England, M. (1999). On the water masses and mean circulation of
703 the South Atlantic Ocean. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *104*(C9),
704 20863–20883. doi: 10.1029/1999JC900139
- 705 Taguchi, B., Nakamura, H., Nonaka, M., Komori, N., Kuwano-Yoshida, A., Takaya,
706 K., & Goto, A. (2012). Seasonal Evolutions of Atmospheric Response to
707 Decadal SST Anomalies in the North Pacific Subarctic Frontal Zone: Observa-
708 tions and a Coupled Model Simulation. *Journal of Climate*, *25*(1), 111–139.
709 doi: 10.1175/JCLI-D-11-00046.1
- 710 Tréguier, A.-M., Deshayes, J., Le Sommer, J., Lique, C., Madec, G., Penduff, T., . . .
711 Talandier, C. (2014). Meridional transport of salt in the global ocean from an
712 eddy-resolving model. *Ocean Science*, *10*(2), 243–255.
- 713 Treguier, A. M., Deshayes, J., Lique, C., Dussin, R., & Molines, J. M. (2012). Eddy
714 contributions to the meridional transport of salt in the North Atlantic. *Journal
715 of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *117*(5). doi: 10.1029/2012JC007927
- 716 Tsujino, H., Nakano, H., Sakamoto, K., Urakawa, L. S., Toyama, K., Kosugi, N., . . .
717 Ishikawa, Y. (2024). Impact of Increased Horizontal Resolution of an Ocean
718 Model on Carbon Circulation in the North Pacific Ocean. *Journal of Advances
719 in Modeling Earth Systems*, *16*(1). doi: 10.1029/2023MS003720
- 720 van der Boog, C. G., Dijkstra, H. A., Pietrzak, J. D., & Katsman, C. A. (2022).
721 Spatial Variations of Antarctic Intermediate Water in the Caribbean Sea Due
722 To Vertical Mixing Along Its Path. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *49*(3),
723 e2021GL095977. doi: 10.1029/2021GL095977
- 724 Weijer, W., Cheng, W., Drijfhout, S. S., Fedorov, A. V., Hu, A., Jackson, L. C., . . .
725 Zhang, J. (2019). Stability of the atlantic meridional overturning circulation:
726 A review and synthesis. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *124*(8),
727 5336–5375.
- 728 Weijer, W., & van Sebille, E. (2014). Impact of Agulhas Leakage on the Atlantic
729 Overturning Circulation in the CCSM4. *Journal of Climate*, *27*(1), 101–110.
730 doi: 10.1175/JCLI-D-12-00714.1
- 731 Williams, K. D., Copsey, D., Blockley, E. W., Bodas-Salcedo, A., Calvert, D.,
732 Comer, R., . . . Xavier, P. K. (2018). The Met Office Global Coupled Model
733 3.0 and 3.1 (GC3.0 and GC3.1) Configurations. *Journal of Advances in Model-
734 ing Earth Systems*, *10*(2), 357–380. doi: 10.1002/2017MS001115

- 735 Yao, W., Shi, J., & Zhao, X. (2017). Freshening of Antarctic Intermediate Water in
736 the South Atlantic Ocean in 2005–2014. *Ocean Science*, *13*(4), 521–530. doi:
737 10.5194/os-13-521-2017
- 738 Youngs, M. K., & Johnson, G. C. (2015, 8). Basin-Wavelength Equatorial Deep Jet
739 Signals across Three Oceans. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, *45*(8), 2134–
740 2148. doi: 10.1175/JPO-D-14-0181.1
- 741 Zhu, C., Liu, Z., & Gu, S. (2018). Model bias for South Atlantic Antarctic interme-
742 diate water in CMIP5. *Climate Dynamics*, *50*(9-10), 3613–3624. doi: 10.1007/
743 s00382-017-3828-1
- 744 Zweng, M., Seidov, D., Boyer, T., Locarnini, M., Garcia, H., Mishonov, A., . . . oth-
745 ers (2019). World ocean atlas 2018, volume 2: Salinity.